

DERIVATION OF A NUMERICAL SCHEME FOR THE THIRD ORDER BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEMS IN ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS USING MAXIMA

Ramani J.V.

*Department of Mathematics, Dyal Singh College (University of Delhi),
Lodhi Road, New Delhi India*

Abstract

In this paper, we present a derivation of a numerical scheme to solve third order boundary value problems using the open source computer algebra system MAXIMA.

Keywords: Boundary Value Problems, Finite Difference, Taylor series, Row Sum Norm, Maximum Error, computer algebra system, MAXIMA.

1. Introduction

An efficient method for solving third order boundary value problems was proposed by the author with Dinesh Kumar in [1].

In this paper, we present the MAXIMA code to derive the schemes used in the papers [1].

2. The Difference method

Recall the scheme presented in the paper[1] :

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} - 2u_{i+\frac{1}{2}} + u_{i+\frac{3}{2}} &= h^2 u''_{i-1} + \frac{h^3}{24} (25u'''_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + 11u'''_{i+\frac{1}{2}}) + T_i, i = 1 \\
 -u_{i-\frac{3}{2}} + 3u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} - 3u_{i+\frac{1}{2}} + u_{i+\frac{3}{2}} &= \frac{h^3}{2} (u'''_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + u'''_{i+\frac{1}{2}}) + T_i, 1 < i < \frac{N}{2} \\
 -u_{i-\frac{3}{2}} + 6u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + 3u_{i+\frac{1}{2}} &= 8u_i - \frac{h^3}{16} (u'''_{i-\frac{3}{2}} - 9u'''_{i-\frac{1}{2}}) + T_i, i = \frac{N}{2} \\
 -u_{i-\frac{5}{2}} + 3u_{i-\frac{3}{2}} - 3u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + u_{i+\frac{1}{2}} &= \frac{h^3}{2} (u'''_{i-\frac{3}{2}} + u'''_{i-\frac{1}{2}}) + T_i, \frac{N}{2} < i < N \\
 u_{i-\frac{5}{2}} - 3u_{i-\frac{3}{2}} + 2u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} &= hu'_i - \frac{h^3}{48} (25u'''_{i-\frac{3}{2}} + 21u'''_{i-\frac{1}{2}}) + T_i, i = N
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

where

$$T_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

is the truncation error.

To derive the above equations in MAXIMA we ran the following code in blue(output not shown here):

We start from the case $i = 1$,

```
kill(all);
T0(h):=u0+h*u1+(h^2/factorial(2))*u2+(h^3/factorial(3))*u3+
(h^4/factorial(4))*u4+(h^5/factorial(5))*u5;
T1(h):=u1+h*u2+(h^2/factorial(2))*u3+(h^3/factorial(3))*u4+
(h^4/factorial(4))*u5+(h^5/factorial(5))*u6;
T2(h):=u2+h*u3+(h^2/factorial(2))*u4+(h^3/factorial(3))*u5+
(h^4/factorial(4))*u6+(h^5/factorial(5))*u7;
T3(h):=u3+h*u4+(h^2/factorial(2))*u5+(h^3/factorial(3))*u6+
(h^4/factorial(4))*u7+(h^5/factorial(5))*u8;
```

```
e1:h^3*(a0*T3(h/2)+a1*T3(3*h/2));
e2:c0*T0(h/2)+c1*T0(3*h/2)+c2*T0(5*h/2);
e3:b0*h^2*T2(0);
```

```
e4:expand(e1)+expand(e2)+expand(e3);
```

```
e5:expand(e4);
```

```
eq:makelist(coeff(e5, h, k)=0, k, 0, 4);
```

```
sol:linsolve(eq, [a0, a1, b0, c0, c1, c2]);
```

```
psol:ev(sol, %r1=1);
```

For the cases $1 < i < \frac{N}{2}$ and $\frac{N}{2} < i < N$, first define $T_0(h), \dots, T_3(h)$ as above and then do

```
e1:h^3*(a0*T3(-h/2)+a1*T3(h/2));
e2:c0*T0(-3*h/2)+c1*T0(-h/2)+c2*T0(h/2)+c3*T0(3*h/2);
```

!

```

e3:expand(e1)+expand(e2);
e4:expand(e3);
eq:makelist(coeff(e3, h, k)=0, k, 0, 4);
sol:linsolve(eq, [a0, a1, c0, c1, c2, c3]);
psol:ev(sol, %r1=1);

```

Similarly for the remaining cases in (2.1).

3. Verification of u values

The values u_i , $i = 0, 1, \dots, N$ are given in [1] as

$$u_{j-1} = \begin{cases} \frac{3h^2}{8}u''_{j-1} - \frac{1}{2}\left(u_{j+\frac{1}{2}} - 3u_{j-\frac{1}{2}}\right) & \text{if } j = 1 \\ \frac{1}{2}\left(u_{j-\frac{3}{2}} + u_{j-\frac{1}{2}}\right) & \text{if } j = 2, \dots, \frac{N}{2} - 1, \frac{N}{2} + 3, \dots, N \\ \left(2u_{j-\frac{1}{2}} - u_j\right) & \text{if } j = \frac{N}{2} \\ \left(2u_{j-\frac{3}{2}} - u_{j-2}\right) & \text{if } j = \frac{N}{2} + 2 \\ \left(u_{j-\frac{3}{2}} + \frac{h}{2}u'_{j-1}\right) & \text{if } j = N + 1 \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

We present the case for $j = 1$ only.

First define $T_0(h), \dots, T_3(h)$ as done above for the scheme and then as follows:

```

e1:a*T0(3*h/2)+b*T0(h/2)+c*h^2*T3(0);
e2:expand(e1);

e3:T0(3*h/2)-3*T0(h/2);
e4:expand(e3);

e5:(1/2)*(3*T0(3*h/2)-T0(h/2));
e6:expand(e5);

e7:T0(0)-((3*h^2*T2(0)/8)-(1/2)*(T0(3*h/2)-3*T0(h/2)));
e8:expand(e7);

```

The codes for verification of the remaining cases are similar.

4. Derivation of Truncation Errors

The truncation errors are given in [1] as

$$T_i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{24}h^5u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(5)} & \text{if } i = 1 \\ \frac{1}{240}h^7u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(7)} & \text{if } i = 2 \\ \vdots & \vdots \end{cases} \left| \left| \frac{1}{240}h^7u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(7)} \right| \right| \left| \left| \text{if } i = \frac{N}{2} + 1 \right| \right| \left| \left| \vdots \right| \right| \left| \left| \frac{31}{1920}h^5u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(5)} \right| \right| \left| \left| \text{if } i = N \right| \right| \quad (4.1)$$

which were derived from the MAXIMA code:

```

For the case  $i = 1$ ,
kill(all);
A(h):=u0+h*u1+(h^2/2)*u2+(h^3/6)*u3+(h^4/24)*u4+
(h^5/120)*u5+(h^6/720)*u6+(h^7/5040)*u7;
A1(h):=u1+h*u2+(h^2/2)*u3+(h^3/6)*u4+(h^4/24)*u5+
(h^5/120)*u6+(h^6/720)*u7;
A2(h):=u2+h*u3+(h^2/2)*u4+(h^3/6)*u5+(h^4/24)*u6+
(h^5/120)*u7;
A3(h):=u3+h*u4+(h^2/2)*u5+(h^3/6)*u6+(h^4/24)*u7;

```

```

lhs:A(0)-2*A(h)+A(2*h);
LHS:expand(lhs);
rhs:h^2*A2(-h/2)+(h^3/24)*(25*A3(0)+11*A3(h));
RHS:expand(rhs);
T:LHS-RHS;

```

For the cases $1 < i < \frac{N}{2}$ and $\frac{N}{2} < i < N$, first define $T0(h), \dots, T3(h)$ as above and then do

```
lhs:-A(-h)+3*A(0)-3*A(h)+A(2*h);
LHS:expand(lhs);
rhs:(h^3/2)*(A3(0)+A3(h));
RHS:expand(rhs);
T:LHS-RHS;
```

Similarly for the remaining cases in (4.1).

5. Upper Bound for $\|A^{-1}\|$

To get an estimate for $\|A^{-1}\|$, we define the matrix A and find its inverse to find an upper bound

```
Penta(N):=block(
  [i, j, k],
  A:zeromatrix(N, N),
  A[1, 1]:a,
  A[1, 2]:b,
  A[1, 3]:c,

  A[(N/2), (N/2)-1]:-1,
  A[(N/2), (N/2)]:6,
  A[(N/2), (N/2)+1]:3,

  A[N, N - 2]: 1,
  A[N, N - 1]: -3,
  A[N, N]: 2,
  k:1,
  for i:2 thru (N-1) do
  (
    if(i#(N/2)) then
    (
      A[i, k]: -1,
      A[i, k + 1]:3,
      A[i, k + 2]:-3,
      A[i, k + 3]:1,
      k:k+1
    )
  ),
  return(A)
);

for i:4 thru 14 step 2 do print(i, " ", determinant(Penta(i)));

for i:4 thru 12 step 2 do print(i, " ", invert(Penta(i)));
```

From these observations an upper bound for $\|A^{-1}\|$ can be found.

References

1. J V Ramani and Dinesh Kumar, A finite difference technique for the solution of third order boundary value problems in ordinary differential equations, Slovak international scientific journal # 81, (2024), 42-46.
2. Maxima Manual, <https://maxima.sourceforge.io/ext/maxima.pdf>
3. numerical.mac, <https://github.com/ramaniji/numericalMethods/blob/main/numerical.mac>.